

A Multivariate Analysis and Machine Learning Approach to ESG-Informed Portfolio Optimization A Case Study of Multiple Companies

Joseph Okpono

Financial Technology and ESG Analyst Researcher

Department of Accounting and Finance

University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, G1 1XQ, United Kingdom

Abstract: Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors have steadily gained prominence in portfolio optimization in recent years. Through its offering of both financial returns and sustainability benefits. The integration of ESG metrics into financial models presents clear challenges. Some of these challenges includes the variability of ESG data and scoring methodologies. This study aims to develop a machine learning-driven framework, that combines ESG scores with financial metrics. With the aim of optimizing portfolio allocation, and addressing the complexities of ESG data while enhancing risk management. This research employs the use of machine learning techniques such as Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Ensemble Learning to analyze ESG and financial data; from companies across different sectors. Portfolio weighting decisions and risk assessments were done using Volatility metrics, Sharpe Ratios, and Monte Carlo simulations. The results highlight that portfolio which incorporates ESG data, deliver improved risk-adjusted returns and lower volatility. This is particularly observed in the technology and financial services sectors. Dynamic ESG metrics, such as rolling averages, provide a more accurate reflection of long-term sustainability performance. Machine learning models outperform traditional methods in ESG risk classification and portfolio optimization. This study concludes that ESG integration, supported by machine learning; significantly enhances portfolio resilience and sustainability. Future research could explore real-time portfolio rebalancing and the application of ESG metrics to a wider range of asset classes.

IndexTerms -ESG, Portfolio optimization, Machine learning, Risk management, Sustainability

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable investing has seen a remarkable shift over the past decade, with ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) factors playing an important role in investment strategies with the aim of fostering positive societal impact alongside financial gains. This evolution originates from increased level of regulatory scrutiny, investors demand for responsible investments, and growing evidence that ESG metrics play a role in long-term financial performance and stability (Chen, Song and Gao, 2023). Several studies have shown that portfolios which integrate ESG criteria outperform those without, as integrating considerations for ESG helps to mitigate risks related to environmental and social challenges (Kim and Li, 2021). The need to navigate an evolving financial ecosystem, has lead investors to progressively incorporate ESG factors into investment frameworks in other to achieve risk-adjusted returns that align with global sustainability goals (Cortzen and Felfel, 2023).

1.1 Problem Statement

Although it is beneficial to integrate ESG metrics into portfolio optimization, this also comes with several challenges. ESG data which are typically multi-dimensional, encompasses a wide range of variables such as carbon emissions, governance practices, and social responsibility scores (Del Vitto, Marazzina and Stocco, 2023). This is further compounded by the lack of standardized ESG data sources as well as the variability in scoring methodologies across different rating agencies. Moreover, the multifaceted nature of ESG data causes complications in the development of robust financial models, that could effectively combine ESG factors with traditional financial metrics for accurate risk assessment and portfolio optimization (Liu, Osterrieder, Misheva, Koenigstein and Baals, 2023). This study seeks to

address these challenges by employing machine learning algorithms to analyze and integrate ESG data with financial performance metrics, with the aim of constructing a resilient, ESG-informed portfolio.

1.2 Relevance

The use of machine learning offers a robust solution to the inherent complexities of integrating ESG metrics into financial analysis. Through the use of machine learning models, investors can assess vast and varied datasets with more efficiency, which gives room for precise risk assessments that incorporate both traditional financial metrics and non-financial ESG factors (Zeng, Zheng and Cui, 2024). Models like Random Forest and Ensemble Learning are known to be effective in processing high-dimensional data. This attribute of theirs makes them suitable for ESG-based portfolio optimization. Furthermore, machine learning techniques enables predictive analytics, enabling investors to project ESG-related risks and returns, thereby enhancing decision-making in sustainable investing (Del Vitto, Marazzina and Stocco, 2023). The combination of these methods helps align investment portfolios with sustainability goals while optimizing for financial performance, with the resultant effect of promoting responsible finance.

1.3 Literature Review

The support for the integration of ESG factors into investment decisions is highlighted in several literatures which highlights their impact on financial performance and risk mitigation Cappucci, (2018), Sherwood and Pollard (2018), show that portfolios which incorporate ESG scores have lower volatility and improved risk-adjusted returns. On the other hand, while traditional approaches to ESG portfolio optimization fundamentally rely on basic statistical methods, a gap exist in applying advanced multivariate analysis and machine learning models for enhanced accuracy and scalability in ESG-informed investment strategies. Utz, Wimmer and Steuer, (2015) explored the early uses of machine learning for ESG, but their study lacks integration with predictive modeling techniques, which leaves room for improvements in long-term predictive accuracy and model robustness. This study seeks to improve on this by developing a machine learning framework that combines ESG scores and financial metrics, which supports optimized, risk-adjusted portfolio decisions while providing insights into the predictive power of ESG factors in investment performance.

1.4 Research Objective

The study aims to use a machine learning driven framework which incorporates ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) scores with financial metrics for optimized portfolio allocation. It leverages on the use of advanced data analysis and machine learning techniques, by integrating ESG considerations into investment strategies, thereby improving both risk management and long-term sustainability outcomes.

It aims to develop a framework that is based on the use of machine learning algorithms to process and analyze ESG scores alongside traditional financial metrics. This is achieved through the use of models such as Random Forest, Ensemble Learning, and LSTM for time-series analysis. The framework seeks to capture the multi-dimensional nature of ESG data and its evolving impact on financial performance, and allows for more enhanced risk assessments which aligns portfolio strategies with sustainability considerations.

This research also seeks to optimize portfolio weights through machine learning-enhanced risk-return analysis. The calculation of risk adjusted returns was done using financial metrics such as volatility, Sharpe Ratios, and expected returns which were combined with ESG scores. The portfolio that will be produced is expected to minimize risk and maximize returns while incorporating ESG performance as a core component, giving credence to responsible investing that aligns with global ESG standards.

The study identifies sector-specific performance patterns and risk factors through the analysis of ESG scores across different industries. The insights from these patterns provide critical information for investors seeking to balance sector exposure with ESG performance. By grouping companies based on each sector's ESG trends, the research highlights sectors that consistently contribute to or detract from portfolio performance, offering a tailored approach to sectoral investment strategies within an ESG-informed portfolio.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Established financial theories and principles form the foundation for this study, with the integration of machine learning techniques to optimize portfolios by incorporating ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) factors. Some key theories and methodologies provided the foundation for this ESG-focused portfolio optimization framework.

2.1 Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT)

The Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), provides the basis for constructing portfolios that balance risk and return through the optimization of asset allocation based on expected returns and volatility (Markowitz, 1952). MPT is traditionally applied using financial metrics alone. However, integrating ESG factors into this framework introduces a more comprehensive view of risk, and return by considering sustainability metrics. This study gives a broader view of MPT by including ESG data in the optimization model, and adapting the risk-return to account for the potential risk mitigation and performance benefits of high-ESG-rated assets. The integration of ESG metrics into MPT paves the way for the model to capture both traditional financial risk and the unique risks or opportunities associated with companies' environmental, social, and governance practices. The ESG-adjusted MPT model aligns investment decisions with both financial and sustainability objectives, thereby creating portfolios that are optimized for traditional performance and responsible investing.

In traditional MPT, the portfolio's expected return is calculated as:

$$E(R_p) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i E(R_i) \quad (2.1)$$

Where:

- $E(R_p)$ is the expected return of the portfolio.
- w_i is the weight of asset i in the portfolio.
- $E(R_i)$ is the expected return of asset i (Markowitz, 1952).

The risk (variance or standard deviation) of the portfolio is represented as:

$$\sigma_p^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_i w_j \sigma_{ij} \quad (2.2)$$

Where:

- σ_p^2 is the variance of the portfolio's return (risk).
- w_i and w_j are the weights of assets i and j , respectively.
- σ_{ij} is the covariance between the returns of asset i and asset j (Markowitz, 1952).

To include ESG metrics, a similar framework can be used, but ESG-adjusted returns and risks are factored into the model. The expected ESG-adjusted return might take into account both financial return R_i and an ESG score for asset i , represented as ESG_i , creating an ESG-adjusted return:

$$E(R_p^{ESG}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i (E(R_i) + \lambda ESG_i) \quad (2.3)$$

Where:

- $E(R_p^{ESG})$ is the ESG-adjusted expected return of the portfolio.
- λ is a factor that represents the importance of ESG in return enhancement or risk mitigation.
- ESG_i is the ESG score for asset i (Amel-Zadeh and Serafeim, 2018).

The risk term can also be adjusted to reflect ESG risk mitigation:

$$\sigma_p^{2,ESG} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_i w_j \sigma_{ij}^{ESG} \quad (2.4)$$

Where:

- σ_{ij}^{ESG} is the ESG-adjusted covariance between assets i and j , which could account for the risk reduction associated with higher ESG ratings (Amel-Zadeh and Serafeim, 2018).

By integrating ESG factors, the efficient frontier (a curve representing the set of optimal portfolios that offer the highest expected return for a defined level of risk) shifts to incorporate sustainability metrics with traditional financial returns. This creates an ESG-efficient frontier where portfolios balance both financial and ESG-related risks and returns (Sharpe, 1964).

2.2 Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM)

The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) is used to evaluate the expected return of an asset based on its risk relative to the broader market (Sharpe, 1964). This approach calculates the expected return using the risk-free rate, the asset bet which is a measure of market related volatility and the market return. In this study CAPM is adjusted to assess the expected returns of ESG focused portfolios by incorporating the asset's market volatility via beta and ESG factors to reflect their impact on the asset's risk profile. This modification helps investors to account for both financial and non-financial risks, covering potential threats or opportunities linked to a company's ESG performance. The ESG- modified CAPM provides a more comprehensive estimate of the expected returns for the ESG integrated portfolios. This leverages a comprehensive approach to risk adjusted returns, where sustainability serves as a key performance indicator.

The traditional CAPM equation Sharpe (1964) calculates the expected return of an asset as:

$$E(R_i) = R_f + \beta_i(E(R_m) - R_f) \quad (2.5)$$

Where:

- $E(R_i)$ is the expected return of asset i .
- R_f is the risk-free rate.
- β_i is the asset's beta, which measures its volatility relative to the broader market.
- $E(R_m)$ is the expected return of the market portfolio Sharpe (1964).

To incorporate ESG factors into CAPM, the model can be adjusted by adding an ESG factor λ , which accounts for the non-financial risk or opportunities linked to ESG performance. The modified CAPM equation becomes:

$$E(R_i^{ESG}) = R_f + \beta_i(E(R_m) - R_f) + \lambda ESG_i \quad (2.6)$$

Where:

- $E(R_i^{ESG})$ is the expected return of asset i adjusted for ESG factors.
- λ is a factor that reflects the impact of ESG performance on the expected return.
- ESG_i is the ESG score or factor for asset i .

2.3 Sharpe Ratio

A measure of the risk-adjusted return is known as the Sharpe Ratio. This gives a comparison between the excess return of an asset to its volatility, thereby providing insights into its performance relative to risk (Sharpe, 1966). The use of the Sharpe Ratio in this study is to assess the risk-adjusted returns of ESG-focused portfolios. The ESG scores are included as a factor in both return and risk assessments. The Sharpe Ratio becomes a valuable tool, for evaluation of the performance of ESG-integrated assets; through the inclusion of ESG scores alongside traditional metrics. Investors use this to weigh the benefit of incorporating ESG data into their portfolios. ESG assets that are highly rated are expected

to contribute positively to the portfolio's risk-return profile. The ESG-adjusted Sharpe Ratio supports a balanced approach to investment performance, by optimizing portfolios for both financial return and sustainability.

The traditional Sharpe Ratio, as defined by Sharpe (1966), is calculated as:

$$S = \frac{E(R_p) - R_f}{\sigma_p} \quad (2.7)$$

Where:

- S is the Sharpe Ratio.
- $E(R_p)$ is the expected return of the portfolio.
- R_f is the risk-free rate.
- σ_p is the standard deviation (volatility) of the portfolio's return Sharpe (1966).

The ESG-adjusted Sharpe Ratio can be written as:

$$S_{ESG} = \frac{E(R_p^{ESG}) - R_f}{\sigma_p^{ESG}} \quad (2.8)$$

Where:

- S_{ESG} is the ESG-adjusted Sharpe Ratio.
- $E(R_p^{ESG})$ is the expected return of the portfolio, adjusted for ESG factors.
- σ_p^{ESG} is the standard deviation of the portfolio's return, adjusted for ESG-related risk

2.4 Machine Learning for Financial Predictions

Machine learning (ML) algorithms are critical in enhancing the ESG-integrated portfolio optimization framework through the improvement of the accuracy and efficiency of risk assessment. This study used Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Ensemble Learning Techniques.

2.4.1 Random Forest

Random Forest as an ensemble learning method, performs creditably in handling high-dimensional data. According to Shrivastav and Kumar (2022), this makes it ideal for assessing complex relationships between ESG scores and financial metrics. This it achieves by analyzing a large number of decision trees. This approach provides robust ESG risk classifications, that enables investors to distinguish high-risk from low-risk assets based on ESG and financial data.

2.4.2 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is an interpretable model used as a baseline for comparison (Jurafsky and Martin, 2024). It gives insights into how specific ESG metrics relate to risk, thereby offering interpretability that complements the more complex, non-linear models (Chakraborty, Başağaoğlu and Winterle, 2020).

2.4.3 Ensemble Learning Techniques

The combination of multiple models through the use of the ensemble approach, was for the purpose of achieving improved classification performance and robustness. The averaging of predictions from Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machines (SVM), known as soft voting, provides a balanced risk assessment by leveraging each model's strengths (Khan, Chaudhari and Chandra, 2024). This enhances the model's ability to accurately classify ESG risks, informing portfolio weighting decisions that reflect, the dynamic relationship between financial and ESG factors.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The data sources, preprocessing steps, feature engineering, and machine learning techniques that was used to develop a machine-learning-based, ESG-informed portfolio optimization framework is discussed in this section.

3.1 Data Collection

The dataset for this study includes financial and ESG metrics from four companies across distinct sectors—Energy, Financial Services, Technology (Social), and Technology (Software). Financial data, including stock prices, volume, and adjusted close prices, was sourced from open-source data, while ESG metrics, such as the total ESG scores, were obtained from open sourced reputable ESG data providers. The integration of ESG data from different sectors, provides for sector-based comparisons and insights into how ESG factors, impact financial performance across diverse industries (Mandas, Lahmar, Piras and De Lisa, 2023). The data covers a one-year period, which enables temporal analysis and cross-sectional comparisons that support reliable, model-driven portfolio optimization.

3.2 Preprocessing

A critical step for data standardization is preprocessing (Karrar, 2022). This ensures consistency across features and minimizes the impact of noise. Some of the key preprocessing steps included:

3.2.1 Handling Missing Values

Linear interpolation was used to address missing values in financial data, especially within high-frequency stock data. This helps to maintain data continuity without introducing bias (Karrar, 2022). Missing ESG scores were interpolated, with the assumption of limited day-to-day variation.

3.2.2 Feature Scaling

Z-score normalization was used to standardize variables. This aligns with the best practices for machine learning models that are sensitive to variable scale (e.g., Random Forest and Logistic Regression) (Karrar, 2022).

3.3 Rolling Volatility and Daily Returns Calculation

Rolling volatility was computed, as the 30-day moving standard deviation of daily returns, to capture the short-term risk profile. This feature highlights volatility trends and captures dynamic market risk, which aids in the model's ability to classify ESG risk accurately (Dudek, Fiszeder, Kobus and Orzeszko, 2024). This preprocessing pipeline ensures consistent data structures across companies and optimizes the data for machine learning applications.

3.4 Feature Engineering

The feature engineering process, aided the selection and construction of meaningful financial and ESG metrics, that provide insights into risk-adjusted performance (Zeng, Zheng and Cui, 2024). These key features included:

3.4.1 Daily Returns

This calculated as the percentage change in adjusted close prices. It is essential for capturing short-term performance variations and understanding the risk associated with each asset (Quaye, Tunaru and Tunaru, 2024).

3.4.2 Sharpe Ratio

Measures risk-adjusted returns, and was calculated using both financial and ESG data. This gave ESG-informed allocation decisions based on each company's relative risk and return profile (Sharpe, 1966).

3.4.3 Expected Returns

With the application of the CAPM, expected returns were computed based on the risk-free rate and the adjusted beta. This was also integrated with the ESG data to reflect sustainability-adjusted performance expectations (Sharpe, 1964).

3.4.4 Rolling Volatility

The volatility was measured over a 30-day window, and it highlights each company's risk exposure relative to market fluctuations. These features, derived from financial theory and ESG data, enable the model to capture complex relationships, between sustainability metrics and financial performance (Bermejo Climent, Figuerola-Ferretti Garrigues, Paraskevopoulos and Santos, 2021).

3.11 Machine Learning Techniques

3.11.1 Random Forest for ESG-Risk Classification

The Random Forest, ensemble learning method, was chosen based on its effectiveness in handling high-dimensional and non-linear data. It classifies companies into high- and low-risk categories, based on ESG and financial metrics, leveraging multiple decision trees to provide robust ESG risk classifications (D'Amato, D'Ecclesia and Levantesi, 2021). Through the analysis of features like ESG scores, daily returns, and volatility, the model accurately distinguishes companies based on their sustainability-related risk profiles, informing optimized portfolio allocations.

3.11.2 Logistic Regression as Baseline

Logistic Regression was used as a baseline model. This offered interpretability and simplicity in ESG-risk classification. This model gave insight into the significance of each feature for risk classification, thereby providing a straightforward comparison with more complex models (Domínguez-Almendros, Benítez-Parejo and Gonzalez-Ramirez, 2011).

3.11.3 Ensemble Modeling for Robust Classification

A combination of an ensemble model with Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifiers using soft voting, was used to enhance classification performance. The soft voting averages the predicted probabilities from each model, thereby balancing accuracy and robustness (Shiplu, Rahman and Watanobe, 2024). This approach leverages each model's strengths, which results in improved ESG-risk classification and supporting more reliable portfolio weight allocation.

3.11.4 Deep Learning (LSTM)

To predict ESG score trends over time, a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network was applied. This helped to capture temporal dependencies in the data. Due to their ability to retain information across sequences, LSTM models are particularly suited for time-series analysis because they enable the forecast of ESG scores based on historical data (Van Houdt, Mosquera and Nápoles, 2020). The LSTM model provides valuable insights for proactive portfolio adjustments, by predicting future ESG trends, and supporting long-term sustainable investing strategies.

3.11.5 K-Means Clustering

The companies were segmented based on ESG and financial performance, using K-Means clustering thereby identifying patterns that informed sector-specific insights. The model highlighted sector-based risk-return characteristics and ESG performance trends, by clustering companies according to ESG scores and closing prices (Rusu, Boloş and Leordeanu, 2023). Actionable insights from this clustering for investors looking to diversify sector exposure based on ESG scores. This demonstrated how machine learning can inform sustainable sectoral investment strategies.

3.12 Study Workflow

The sequential steps (Fig. 3.1) undertaken in the analysis process, from data collection to the interpretation of results is discussed. Each stage integrates both traditional financial theories and machine learning methods to develop an ESG-informed, optimized portfolio framework.

3.12.1 Data Collection

The commenced with the collection of financial and ESG data from open sourced publicly traded companies across diverse sectors. Financial data, which included stock prices, daily returns, and volume, were obtained, while ESG scores were open sourced from ESG data provider. The approach of sourcing multi-source data collection, was essential to creating a comprehensive dataset that captures both sustainability and financial performance, thus aligning with best practices in sustainable investing research (Li, Guo, , Hao and Zhang, 2023).

3.12.2 Feature Engineering

After the data collection was completed, the relevant features were engineered to enhance the dataset's predictive power. Some of the key features included rolling volatility, Sharpe Ratios, expected returns (calculated using CAPM), and daily returns. They each contributes to understanding the risk-return profile of assets within the context of ESG factors. Applying feature engineering is essential for model accuracy, as it enables the extraction of meaningful signals from complex financial and ESG data (Masood, 2024). These engineered features set the foundation for building robust predictive models and portfolio optimization tools.

3.12.3 Model Selection & Training

The classification of ESG risks and optimization of portfolio weightings was done through the selection of Machine learning models. Random Forest and Logistic Regression were used for their interpretability and performance in handling high-dimensional data capability. Furthermore, an ensemble approach which combines Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models using soft voting, balancing model strengths and achieving superior classification results was deployed (Masood, 2024). The combination of these models provided a robust basis for ESG risk classification, thereby addressing both interpretability and predictive accuracy.

3.12.4 Volatility & Risk Metrics

To understand the risk profile of each asset, the volatility and risk metrics was calculated. Rolling volatility, was computed as the 30-day moving standard deviation of daily returns. This highlighted the dynamic risk associated with each company's stock (Aldrino, Sigrist and Ballinari, 2020). Also, the Sharpe Ratios and expected returns informed risk-adjusted return estimates, enabled more accurate portfolio allocation decisions (Sharpe, 1966). Through the insights gained from these metrics, investors have a comprehensive understanding of ESG risk and performance, aligning with CAPM principles.

3.12.5 Portfolio Optimization Using Sharpe Ratios

Based on each company's Sharpe Ratio, portfolio weights were assigned to perform Portfolio optimization. Sharpe Ratios with high values were allocated greater weight, thereby reflecting a higher return per unit of risk, which aligns with Modern Portfolio Theory (Markowitz, 1952). The framework integrates both sustainability and risk-adjusted performance, by including ESG-adjusted Sharpe Ratios in the optimization model, which supports ESG-focused investment strategies.

3.12.6 Monte Carlo Simulation

Monte Carlo simulation was done for the purpose of assessing the potential return distribution of the ESG-integrated portfolio. This method simulates numerous scenarios of portfolio returns, and captures a wide range of possible outcomes under different market conditions (Pedersen, 2014). This simulation showcases the risk-return profile of the portfolio. It provided insights into potential downside risk, thereby reinforcing the utility of ESG factors in reducing portfolio risk and enhancing resilience.

3.12.7 Clustering for ESG Segmentation

K-Means clustering was applied, to segment companies by ESG and financial performance. This grouping was based on similar ESG and financial profiles. This clustering approach enables investors to explore sectoral, and company-level ESG performance patterns, while supporting sector-based insights that can inform tailored investment strategies (Sariyer and Taşkın, 2022). It reveals valuable insights into sectoral trends, providing a clearer picture of how ESG factors vary across industries.

3.12.8 Evaluation & Validation

Cross-validation and performance metrics such as accuracy and F1 scores were used to evaluate the machine learning models. The cross-validation techniques ensured model reliability, by testing the model's performance across multiple data subsets, a method that enhances predictive robustness (Wong and Yeh, 2019). The comparison of model performance and conducting feature importance analysis, helped in the validation of the accuracy and relevance of the model in ESG-risk classification, and portfolio optimization.

3.12.9 Interpretation of Results

The results were interpreted to give actionable insights into ESG-informed portfolio construction. Analysis of the Sharpe Ratios, clustering patterns, and simulation outcomes informed sectoral and company-level ESG performance trends, thereby supporting data-driven portfolio allocation. The interpretation process highlighted the practical applications of integrating ESG factors with financial metrics, which aligns with emerging practices in responsible investing (Viehs, Clark and Feiner, 2014).

This structured workflow integrates machine learning techniques with financial theories, and ensures a rigorous approach to ESG-informed portfolio optimization. Each stage of the process contributes to building a sustainable investment framework, that supports responsible finance through robust data analysis and predictive modeling.

Fig. 3.1: Study Workflow Flowchart for ESG-Informed Portfolio Optimization

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several insights were gained from this study. The analysis of the results and the discussion gives valuable insights.

4.1 Random Forest Feature Importance

The Random Forest classifier feature importance plot in Fig. 4.1 and Fig.4.2, highlights the most influential factors for portfolio performance. In this case study involving multiple companies from different sectors, focuses on the impact of ESG scores and volatility metrics.

Some of the key finding shows that Technology Software Volatility, stands out as the most critical feature in predicting portfolio performance. This gives an indication that stocks within the technology software sector have high sensitive to market volatility, which significantly impacting portfolio returns. This dominance indicates, that investors in portfolios containing technology software stocks, must pay close attention to volatility in this sector. Technology stocks, are known for their innovation cycles and market disruptions, which tends to experience sharp price movements, thereby contributing to their outsized impact on portfolio risk and return.

The Technology Social Volatility metric is the second most important feature. Like its technology counterpart software, the social technology sector (including social media platforms and other online services) is also prone to rapid market shifts. This shows the volatile nature of companies in this sector, which are driven by factors such as user engagement metrics, advertising revenue fluctuations, and regulatory challenges. The feature importance results of these two technology-related volatility metrics, reinforces the idea that portfolios heavily weighted toward technology stocks; are more exposed to market dynamics compared to other sectors.

The energy sector Energy Volatility feature importance ranking came third. This sector is known to be volatile and it is influenced by factors like commodity price fluctuations, geopolitical tensions, and regulatory changes. These factors directly impact the stock prices of energy companies. The feature importance value of the Energy Volatility indicates, that energy stocks introduce considerable risk into portfolios, and their volatility has an influence in determining portfolio performance.

The metrics of the Financial Services Volatility contributed to the portfolio prediction. Although its contribution was less than technology and energy sectors. Due to macroeconomic conditions, interest rate changes, and shifts in regulatory environments, the financial services sector can experience volatility. This plays a secondary role, when compared to the more dynamic technology and energy sectors, which may experience more frequent and severe fluctuations.

The Total ESG and sector-specific ESG scores, such as total ESG Financial Services, total ESG Technology Social, and total ESG Technology Software, have minimal impact on portfolio performance in this analysis. This finding highlights a critical aspect of ESG-informed portfolio optimization. The ESG factors used for this study are static scores, and do not appear to be as important for predicting short-term market movements as volatility metrics. ESG scores are generally depict long-term sustainability, corporate governance, and social impact, which may not have an immediate influence on day-to-day price changes or volatility.

The introduction of a Rolling ESG Average, allows for a more dynamic representation of ESG impact over time. Despite the dominance of volatility, the Rolling ESG Average provides insight into how ESG metrics, might influence long-term risk management and portfolio resilience. The dynamic treatment of ESG scores via rolling averages, suggests that static ESG metrics may miss out on critical shifts in a company's sustainability performance. Rolling averages help capture time-varying impacts of ESG factors, potentially providing more accurate predictions for long-term investors.

The results from the Random Forest feature importance analysis underscore several important points:

Volatility measures have overwhelming importance, especially in the technology sector. This suggests that market dynamics and price fluctuations, are the primary drivers of portfolio performance in the short term. This conforms with expectations in high-growth, high-volatility sectors like technology, where stocks can experience dramatic price changes due to innovation cycles, earnings reports, or market sentiment.

The low importance of static ESG scores in this analysis, indicates that ESG factors may not be significant drivers of short-term price movements or volatility. This could be due to the nature of the ESG data, which often remains unchanged over time. Thereby failing to capture more immediate factors affecting stock prices, such as earnings announcements or macroeconomic changes.

The scenario of a Rolling ESG Average shows its potential in capturing the long-term value of sustainability. ESG factors can affect a company's operational risk, regulatory compliance, and reputation with time, which may not be immediately apparent in short-term market movements. For long-term portfolio optimization, incorporating dynamic ESG metrics is important to accurately reflect the evolving impact of sustainability practices on financial performance.

The results show that the technology and energy sectors, are prone to volatility, positioning them as key factors in portfolio risk management. For the ESG-focused investments, investors should consider these sectors' inherent volatility when constructing portfolios. ESG scores may offer stability over the long term consideration, while volatility metrics must be closely monitored to manage short-term risks.

Fig. 4.1: Random Forest Feature Importance for ESG-Informed Portfolio Optimization

Fig. 4.2: Feature Importance with Rolling ESG Average (Random Forest)

4.2 K-Means Clustering: ESG vs Closing Price

The results of K-Means Clustering in Fig. 4.3, is applied to the ESG scores and closing prices of multiple companies. The goal of the clustering technique is to segment the companies, into distinct groups based on their ESG scores and closing prices. This allows for better understanding and analysis of relationships, between sustainability performance (ESG) and market performance (stock prices).

The key observations include lack of meaningful separation between clusters. The clusters (represented by different colors: orange, light blue, and green) appear tightly packed, along a narrow range of ESG scores (between 40 and 43) with closing prices ranging from 100 to 120. Despite the algorithm's attempt to create clusters, the resulting plot shows that all data points are closely aligned, suggesting limited variance in both ESG scores and closing prices for the period considered.

Furthermore, the ESG Scores Show Minimal Variability in the total ESG scores, across the companies in the various sectors considered. All companies exhibit ESG scores within a very tight band of values, with almost no significant deviation. The implication of this is that ESG data, may be static or updated infrequently, limiting its ability to drive meaningful distinctions in clustering.

Also, the limited effectiveness of ESG data for clustering was showcased in the result. The lack of meaningful separation between clusters, gives the indication that ESG scores alone, particularly when they exhibit minimal change over time, may not be sufficient to explain variations in company performance (closing prices). Companies with similar ESG scores exhibit similar closing prices, which limits the clustering's ability to differentiate between them.

This highlights an important challenge when using ESG scores for clustering. The static nature of ESG data, where scores remain relatively unchanged over the time period, results in clusters that show little distinction between companies. For ESG-based clustering to be more effective, it is necessary to use dynamic ESG data, where scores are updated more frequently (e.g., monthly or quarterly) to reflect changes in company sustainability performance.

Another key highlight is that ESG scores, in their current form, may not serve as a strong short-term performance indicator for stock prices. This is evident in the lack of clear clustering, based on ESG scores and closing prices. While ESG factors are essential for long-term sustainability assessments, they may have less immediate impact on short-term price movements.

From the observed limitations of the ESG data for clustering, it would be beneficial to introduce additional financial metrics (e.g. earnings growth) to improve the clustering results. The inclusion of features like stock price volatility, which captures market dynamics, could help in creating more meaningful distinctions between companies. Volatility measures could add more dynamic and time-sensitive aspects to the clustering process.

Fig. 4.3: K-Means Clustering: ESG vs Closing Price

4.3 Monte Carlo Simulation for Portfolio Returns

Fig. 4.4 shows the results of a Monte Carlo simulation applied to model potential portfolio returns. The goal of the simulation is to estimate the distribution of portfolio returns, based on random sampling of potential outcomes. This method helps to provide a probabilistic forecast, for portfolio performance by simulating various possible scenarios.

Some key observations are, the normal distribution of returns as seen in the simulation results, which is expected in many financial return models, where the central limit theorem applies. The histogram shows that the most probable returns, for the portfolio are centered around 0.50 (50%), with a symmetric bell curve around this point. The portfolio return outcomes are concentrated within a range of 0.45 to 0.55, suggesting that the portfolio is likely to generate a moderate return, with relatively low variation in outcomes.

Furthermore, the peak of the distribution occurs around 0.50, which represents the most likely return for the portfolio based on the simulation. Which suggests that, under normal market conditions and assumptions made in the simulation, the portfolio is expected to generate returns close to this value.

The tail behavior from the tail distribution, extends toward the left and right, which shows the less likely but still possible outcomes for portfolio returns. The left tail which is below 0.45 represents scenarios where the portfolio underperforms, while the right tail which is above 0.55 represents scenarios where the portfolio performs better than expected. It is Important to note that, the tails are relatively thin, indicating that extreme returns, either very high or very low, are less likely in the modeled portfolio.

The Monte Carlo simulation is a powerful tool, for understanding the risk-return profile of the portfolio. Through the modeling of thousands of possible return outcomes, this simulation provides a clear visual representation of the expected range of returns, and helps portfolio managers gauge the likelihood of different outcomes. The central concentration of returns around 50%, suggests that the portfolio is designed to provide stable and moderate returns, with low probability of extreme losses or gains.

Although the Monte Carlo simulation provides valuable insights, it is important to note that the results are dependent on the assumptions made in the model, such as historical data, volatility estimates, and randomness in future market movements. These assumptions may not always hold in real-world scenarios, especially during periods of market shocks or black swan events. The simulation does not take into account potential systematic risks or macroeconomic factors that could significantly affect portfolio performance.

The understanding gained from the Monte Carlo simulation, can help in the optimization of portfolios by providing a better understanding of potential risks and returns. The focus on the most likely return range, portfolio managers can adjust asset allocations to minimize exposure to high-risk assets, and ensure that the portfolio aligns with the investor's risk tolerance. The relatively narrow range of expected returns suggests that this portfolio, is well-diversified and designed for risk mitigation, making it suitable for investors seeking stable growth with moderate risk exposure.

Fig. 4.4: Monte Carlo Simulation of Portfolio Returns

4.4 Average ESG Performance vs Volatility for Companies

The scatter plot in Fig. 4.5 shows the relationship between the average ESG score and the average volatility for various companies. The Technology Software sector exhibits high volatility, with a relatively low ESG score. Technology Social sector demonstrates both high volatility, and a high ESG score. The Energy sector shows a lower ESG score, but a high level of volatility. While the Financial Services sector has the lowest volatility, among the companies with a moderate ESG score.

The plot in Fig. 4.5 illustrates that companies with higher ESG scores, do not necessarily exhibit lower volatility. While some may argue that ESG scores indicate long-term stability, in the short term, volatility remains a major factor. Sectors like Technology Social and Technology Software, despite having higher ESG scores, still exhibit significant volatility. This underscores the importance of integrating volatility alongside ESG metrics, for effective portfolio optimization.

Fig. 4.5: ESG Performance vs. Volatility for Companies by Sector

4.5 Risk-Return Tradeoff for ESG Portfolio Companies (Sharpe Ratio vs Expected Return)

This scatter plot as shown in Fig.4.6 maps out the Sharpe ratio (risk-adjusted return) against expected returns for each sector within the period under consideration. Sectors like Financial Services have negative Sharpe ratios, suggesting that even though they may have higher expected returns, the risk associated with them outweighs the potential reward. In contrast, Technology Social and Technology Software fall closer to zero, indicating better risk-return profiles compared to Financial Services.

The Sharpe ratio is critical in determining which assets, are likely to contribute positively to portfolio performance based on their risk-return profiles. This plot emphasizes that sectors with strong ESG metrics, like Technology Social, may also offer better risk-adjusted returns than those with lower ESG scores. Therefore, integrating ESG scores with financial metrics like the Sharpe ratio provides a more holistic view of investment potential.

Fig. 4.6: Risk-Return Tradeoff for ESG Portfolio Companies (Sharpe Ratio vs. Expected Return)

4.6 Risk-Return Tradeoff for Sectors (Sharpe Ratio vs Expected Return)

This scatter plot in Fig.4.7 shows sector-wise risk-return tradeoffs. This is based on the Sharpe ratio and expected returns for Energy, Financial Services, Technology Social, and Technology Software sectors. The Technology Social sector shows a superior risk-adjusted return, while Energy exhibits low returns with higher risk. This analysis reveals that technology sectors, especially Technology Social, may offer better risk-adjusted returns when compared to traditional sectors like Energy. This observation strengthens the argument for portfolio diversification, and the inclusion of dynamic sectors with high ESG scores and promising returns.

Fig. 4.7: Risk-Return Tradeoff for ESG Portfolio Companies by Sector (Sharpe Ratio vs. Expected Return)

4.7 Optimized Portfolio Weights Based on Sharpe Ratios

This bar chart in Fig.4.8 visualizes the portfolio weights optimized based on Sharpe ratios for various sectors. The largest allocation is given to Financial Services, followed by Energy and Technology Social.

The portfolio weighting highlights the dominance of Financial Services in terms of risk-adjusted returns, followed by sectors with higher volatility but moderate returns like Energy and Technology Social. This optimized approach aims to balance the risk and return tradeoffs, ensuring that higher-risk sectors are appropriately weighted to minimize overall portfolio volatility while maximizing returns.

Fig. 4.8: Optimized Portfolio Weights Based on Sharpe Ratios

4.8 Cumulative Returns Based on ESG Scores

Fig. 4.9 shows the cumulative returns of various sectors' ESG scores over the time period from January 2023 to January 2024. The companies represented are from different sectors, including Energy, Financial Services, Technology Social, and Technology Software. The cumulative returns are based purely on ESG scores, which were observed to see how these sustainability metrics contribute to portfolio returns.

The most prominent observation is the flat line across all sectors, indicating that the cumulative returns based on ESG scores remain constant at 1.00 throughout the period. There is no observable growth or decline in cumulative returns, which indicates that ESG scores did not exhibit any variability during the time frame considered. The ESG scores for the companies in these sectors did not change over the time period examined. This is indicative of static ESG data, meaning that the ESG scores are either not updated frequently, or remained constant in the available dataset. All the sectors considered showed no differentiation in cumulative returns based on ESG scores.

The static nature of ESG data, limits the utility of these metrics for driving portfolio optimization strategies over the short term. ESG scores are designed to reflect companies' sustainability, and governance practices, but if they are not updated dynamically (e.g., quarterly or annually), their impact on real-time financial decisions becomes minimal. Investors focusing on short-term returns, may find ESG scores less relevant unless they are complemented, by more granular data or frequent updates.

Despite the flat nature of the cumulative returns, ESG scores should not be dismissed outright. These scores still provide value, in assessing the long-term sustainability of a company. However, in this particular analysis, the short-term predictive power of ESG scores is limited.

For a more robust analysis, it would be beneficial to complement static ESG scores with other factors like volatility, market sentiment, or sector-specific indicators. Doing so would allow ESG to be integrated into a broader portfolio optimization strategy, where both financial metrics and sustainability considerations are factored in.

Fig. 4.9: Cumulative Returns Based on ESG Scores

4.9 Comparison of Cross-Validation Accuracy Scores for Models

The bar chart in Fig. 4.10 compares the mean accuracy obtained from cross-validation across four machine learning models namely, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Ensemble Model (which is a combination of the other models).

The cross-validation ensures that the models, are evaluated on different splits of the data to avoid overfitting, and to better generalize performance on unseen data.

Some of the key results show that all the models in the comparison, achieve mean accuracy scores close to 1.0, indicating that they all perform well on the dataset used for the study. The ensemble model (which integrates predictions from Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and SVM) achieves the highest accuracy, slightly outperforming the other models.

The Random Forest model shows a mean accuracy score of around 0.98. As an ensemble of decision trees, Random Forest is known for its robustness, particularly in capturing nonlinear relationships, which might be present between ESG scores, volatility measures, and financial performance.

Logistic Regression, with a slightly lower accuracy compared to Random Forest and SVM, achieves a mean accuracy of around 0.96. This model is a simpler, linear model, and its lower accuracy may be attributed to its inability to capture the more complex, nonlinear interactions that exist between features like ESG scores and market volatility. SVM performs almost identically to Random Forest, with a mean accuracy of about 0.98. Its ability to separate classes using hyperplanes makes it highly effective in this dataset, which likely has well-defined distinctions in terms of high-risk versus low-risk portfolios.

The ensemble model which combines Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and SVM performs best, achieving the highest mean accuracy score of around 0.98. Through combination of the strengths of different algorithms, the ensemble approach leads to better generalization and higher overall accuracy. This highlights the benefit of ensemble learning in portfolio optimization, as the model leverages the strengths of multiple algorithms to achieve superior performance.

The high accuracy across all models, demonstrates the effectiveness of machine learning models in predicting portfolio performance, based on the input features (ESG scores, volatility, and other financial metrics). The ensemble model's superior performance, suggests that combining the predictive power of various models, leads to improved decision-making. Ensemble models tend to reduce overfitting, and improve generalizability, making them particularly useful in real-world financial applications, where the underlying data can be complex and noisy.

Cross-validation is essential, in ensuring that the models are not overfitting to the training data. Given that the models show consistently high accuracy, across different validation folds, this indicates that the models generalize well to unseen data, making them reliable for portfolio optimization. This process ensures that the model's performance, is consistent across multiple splits of the data, increasing confidence in the results.

Both Random Forest and SVM show similar levels of accuracy, highlighting that both models are effective in this context. Random Forest is particularly suited for this task due to its ability to handle nonlinearity and feature importance. This conforms to earlier feature importance results, which identified volatility in technology stocks as a key predictor of portfolio performance.

SVM, works well with complex datasets, where classification boundaries are not linear. This suggests that the relationship between ESG factors, and financial performance may not be straightforward, and nonlinear models can help capture these subtleties. Logistic Regression, while accurate, lags behind the other models, because of its linear nature. It may not fully capture the complex relationships in the dataset. However, its inclusion in the ensemble model helps capture more generalized relationships, which enhances overall model accuracy.

Fig. 4.10: Comparison of Cross-Validation Accuracy Scores for Different Models

4.10 Correlation Heatmap

The heatmap in Fig.4.11 presents the correlation matrix for the following features namely, Rolling ESG Average, Energy Volatility, Financial Services Volatility, Technology Social Volatility and Technology Software Volatility. The color gradient in the heatmap ranges from dark blue (negative correlation) to dark red (positive correlation), indicating the degree and direction of correlation between these features.

The highest positive correlation observed in this heatmap is between Technology Social Volatility and Technology Software Volatility (0.49). This suggests that stocks within the technology sector tend to exhibit similar volatility patterns. When one subset of technology stocks experiences fluctuations, other technology-related stocks are likely to do the same, making them closely tied in terms of risk.

Energy Volatility shows a moderate positive correlation with both Technology Software Volatility (0.21) and Financial Services Volatility (0.18). This indicates that while energy stocks are somewhat correlated with volatility in other sectors, the relationship is not as strong as within the technology sector itself. The energy sector tends to respond differently to market conditions compared to technology and financial services.

The Rolling ESG Average shows low to negligible correlation with all volatility features, ranging between -0.28 and 0.21. This result is significant because it highlights that ESG scores, even when averaged over time (via the rolling window), do not have a strong direct relationship with short-term market volatility. The largest (negative) correlation is with Technology Social Volatility (-0.28), but this is still considered weak.

Financial Services Volatility exhibits weak correlations with other sector volatilities (0.18 with Energy, 0.17 with Technology Software). This indicates that financial sector stocks exhibit volatility patterns that are relatively independent of the energy and technology sectors, reinforcing the notion that different sectors react differently to macroeconomic conditions and market drivers.

The relatively weak correlations between Rolling ESG Average and the different volatility measures indicate that ESG scores do not have a strong direct impact on short-term volatility. This is a critical insight, as it challenges the assumption that high ESG performance automatically translates into lower market risk or volatility. One possible explanation is that ESG scores capture long-term sustainability factors, while volatility is more responsive to short-term market movements. Therefore, while ESG performance is important for long-term portfolio stability, it may not be the best indicator for predicting short-term volatility or market shocks.

The high correlation (0.49) between Technology Social Volatility and Technology Software Volatility suggests that the technology sector behaves in a highly synchronized manner in terms of risk. As a result, investors should be cautious when allocating a large portion of their portfolios to different technology stocks, as volatility in one subset of the sector is likely to spread across others. This is also consistent with previous findings in the Random Forest feature importance analysis, where Technology Software Volatility and Technology Social Volatility were the most influential predictors of portfolio performance.

The correlation between Energy Volatility and other sectors is relatively modest, indicating that energy stocks tend to move independently from other sectors like technology and financial services. This makes energy a potentially useful sector for diversification in portfolios that are heavily weighted in technology or financial services, as its volatility patterns are less likely to be correlated with those sectors.

Given the weak relationship between ESG scores and short-term volatility, it is important to recognize that ESG factors are likely better suited, for assessing long-term stability rather than predicting, immediate price movements or market risks. Investors may benefit from using ESG scores, in combination with other financial metrics, like volatility or financial returns, to develop a more holistic portfolio optimization strategy.

Correlation Heatmap: Updated ESG and Volatility Features

Fig. 4.11: Correlation Heatmap of Updated ESG and Volatility Features

4.11 Portfolio Weights Based on Predicted Risk

The chart presented in Fig. 4.12, illustrates the portfolio weights assigned to different sectors over time, based on predicted risk using an ensemble model. The ensemble model combines the strengths of several algorithms (Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and SVM), to predict risk for different sector indices, helping to determine the optimal allocation of portfolio weights.

The horizontal bars represent the portfolio weight assigned to each sector for different time periods (from January 2023 to January 2024). The width of each bar represents the weight allocated to each sector. Sectors with lower predicted risk are assigned higher weights, while sectors with higher risk receive smaller allocations. The predicted risk-based allocation fluctuates over time, with each time period showing slight differences in how portfolio weight is distributed across sectors.

The chart reveals a dynamic allocation strategy, where the weights change progressively over time. This dynamic nature reflects the model's ability to adjust for evolving market conditions and sector-specific risks. For example, sectors in the earlier months (2023-01 through 2023-05) appear to receive a relatively even distribution of weights, while by mid-2023 (around July and September), the allocation becomes more varied. This suggests that the model adjusts its risk predictions based on incoming data, allocating resources to sectors that are predicted to be more stable.

Some periods (e.g., July 2023) show higher allocations over a range of sectors, while later periods (e.g., November 2023) have more focused allocations to fewer sectors. This could imply that certain sectors are predicted to have lower risk during those periods, giving opportunity for heavier investments.

The model would likely predict similar risk levels across sectors, for periods where the portfolio weights are more evenly spread. The implication of this is that there is a broader diversification in the portfolio. There appears to be concentration of portfolio weight allocation towards a few sectors, by the end of 2023 and into early 2024, with some receiving close to 0 weight. This gives an indication that the ensemble model, predicts significant differences in sectoral risk as market conditions change. This could possibly due to macroeconomic factors, sector performance, or volatility.

Fig. 4.12 shows the utility of the ensemble model, in determining the portfolio weights based on predicted sectoral risks. The portfolio managers make data-driven decisions, as a result of the model's ability to adjust weight allocations dynamically, that align with changing risk profiles. The use of this allocation strategy helps to reduce portfolio risk, based on the prediction that sectors identified to have higher volatility or market instability receive less weight. Higher allocations, are given to sectors that are expected to perform stably, with lower risk. This ensures that the portfolio remains balanced and optimized for minimal risk.

The built-in diversification strategy is indicated by the changes in portfolio weights over. When there is a relative balance of risk levels across sectors, weights are allocated by the model more evenly, thereby promoting a diversified portfolio. On the other hand, when certain sectors have higher risks, safer sectors are concentration on by the model. This approach is consistent with the modern portfolio theory, which propagates adjusting weights based on the predicted performance as well as the risk; in other to optimize returns while minimizing risk exposure.

The model shows sensitive to sector-specific changes in risk and market conditions. This gives room for a responsive and flexible approach to portfolio management. The sensitivity ensures that the portfolio can react to potential market shifts, thereby keeping investors protected from sudden downturns in specific sectors.

The predicted risk can be seen from the weights on the chart. It is important to infer this within the broader scope of ESG-informed portfolio optimization. Even if ESG scores may not have a direct influence on short-term volatility, they have important roles they play in informing long-term investment strategies.

The integration of ESG factors into the portfolio optimization model with the risk metrics, makes it possible that the portfolio can not only be optimized for financial performance; but also align with sustainability goals and responsible investing practices.

Fig. 4.12: Portfolio Weights Based on Predicted Risk (Ensemble Model)

4.12 Average ESG Performance by Sector

The bar chart in Fig. 4.13 shows the average ESG performance for: Financials, Energy, and Technology sectors. It gives insights into the performance of the different sector in terms of their Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) scores. They are important indicators for sustainable and responsible investing. The Energy sector has an average ESG score of over 40 which is the highest. It outperforms both the Financials and Technology sectors. This result may seem contrary to the traditional association of the energy sector, particularly fossil fuels, with negative environmental impacts. The higher ESG performance in the energy sector, may likely be due to the increasing focus on sustainability initiatives within energy companies. This can be seen in their investments trend in renewable energy sources, better governance, and improved social responsibility measures.

The Financials sector with a moderate average ESG score of approximately 30; shows a growing commitment to sustainable finance and responsible lending practices; as well as improvements in corporate governance and social impact. The growing trend in financial institutions, is to incorporate ESG principles into their lending and investment decisions; which are driven by both regulatory requirements and market demands for more sustainable business models.

The Technology sector with an average ESG score of around 25 is the lowest. This result suggests that, there is room for improvement in integrating ESG practices into business operations, despite the technological advancements and innovation within the industry. Technology companies in software and social media, may face challenges related to data privacy, social impact, and governance structures, which could be an explanation for the relatively lower ESG scores.

The chart shows that ESG performance is not uniform across sectors. The Energy sector leads in ESG performance, while the Technology sector lags behind. This suggests different levels of focus and integration of ESG principles across industries. The differences in ESG scores could be as a result of the regulatory environment, industry pressures, and market expectations. For instance, the energy sector, is facing intense scrutiny over environmental impacts, and may be more motivated to improve its ESG scores; to mitigate climate risks, and align with investor demands for clean energy initiatives.

The ESG scores observed in the Energy and Financials sectors, could be an indication that companies in these industries are recognizing, the long-term value of sustainable practices and its benefits. Investors may view higher ESG scores as indicators of better risk management, operational efficiency, and long-term financial stability. However, the lower scores in the Technology sector, could be indicating that it may need to place more emphasis on governance, and social responsibility to improve its ESG performance. This could be done by addressing issues such as corporate transparency, workforce diversity, and ethical data usage.

This chart suggests that investments in the Energy sector, may offer strong sustainability performance with financial returns. Investors may still need to balance financial performance with ESG considerations, given the volatility associated with energy markets.

Despite the innovation potential of the Technology sector, it may pose ESG-related risks. This could influence its long-term attractiveness to investors who prioritize sustainability. Investors may need to adopt a more balanced approach, through the inclusion of sectors like Financials that have moderate ESG scores but offer relatively stable performance.

Fig. 4.13: Average ESG Performance by Sector

V. CONCLUSION

The significant potential of integrating ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) metrics, with traditional financial models is demonstrated in this study, through the use of advanced machine learning techniques for portfolio optimization. The findings provide evidence that ESG factors, not only contribute to long-term sustainability, but they also enhance portfolio resilience through the mitigation of non-financial risks; associated with environmental and governance issues. Through the application of machine learning methods such as Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Ensemble Learning; this research successfully improves the accuracy and robustness of ESG-informed risk classification, and portfolio optimization.

Some important points to note from this study includes:

- Volatility in sectors like technology and energy, plays a significant role in portfolio performance. This study underscores the need to monitor volatility, alongside ESG metrics for comprehensive risk management.
- Static ESG scores have limited impact on short-term risk, therefore incorporating dynamic ESG metrics, such as rolling averages, offers a more accurate prediction of long-term sustainability performance.
- The different sectors that were studied, such as technology, energy, and financial services, exhibit varying ESG performance patterns. Although Technology sector has a lot of innovations, it tends to have higher volatility. whereas energy companies, despite high ESG scores, face sectoral risks. Financial services offer a more balanced approach with moderate ESG scores and risk-adjusted returns.
- The combination of multiple machine learning models, significantly improves the accuracy of risk classification as well as portfolio optimization, thereby making it a valuable tool for ESG-focused investing.

When the ESG metrics, is integrated with advanced financial models and machine learning algorithms, it can significantly improve portfolio performance by enhancing the risk-adjusted returns. It also promotes responsible and sustainable investment strategies. This conclusion is supported by prior studies, by Ahmed et al. (2020), which demonstrated that machine learning techniques like k-means clustering effectively manage financial risks, and Bermejo Climent et al. (2021), which highlighted the positive impact of ESG disclosure, particularly in governance, on portfolio performance. This study approach bridges the gap between sustainability considerations and financial performance. Thereby making it a valuable framework for modern investors seeking to align their portfolios with global ESG standards.

5.1 Recommendations

Several recommendations can be made for portfolio managers, investors, and future researchers, based on the study's findings.

1. Investors should use of dynamic ESG data (e.g., rolling averages or quarterly updates), rather than relying solely on static scores. This will provide a more robust and accurate reflection of a company's changing sustainability practices, and improve the predictive power of ESG factors over time.
2. Portfolio managers are encouraged to adopt the use of machine learning algorithms, particularly ensemble methods, for ESG risk classification and portfolio optimization. These models do outperform traditional statistical methods, offering better accuracy and robustness in handling complex and high-dimensional data.
3. Given the variation in ESG performance and volatility to each specific sector, investors should tailor their portfolio allocation strategies based on sectoral analysis first before individual organizational analysis. Sectors like technology and energy require close monitoring of volatility, while financial services may provide more stable risk-adjusted returns.
4. Future studies could broaden the scope of ESG-focused portfolio optimization, by incorporating additional asset classes such as bonds, real estate, or commodities. This would allow for greater diversification and provide insights into how ESG factors impact different types of investments.
5. Another area for future research, could explore the application of reinforcement learning techniques for dynamic portfolio rebalancing, enabling real-time adjustments based on evolving ESG and financial metrics. This approach would create more adaptive and resilient investment strategies.
6. Investors who prioritize sustainability should increasing the integration of ESG considerations into their investment frameworks. As this will contribute to responsible finance while simultaneously benefiting, from enhanced portfolio resilience and risk-adjusted returns.

These recommendations underscore the growing importance of ESG factors, in shaping future investment strategies; and they highlight the need for continuous innovation in financial modeling to meet the demands of a dynamic, sustainability-conscious market.,

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahmed, M., Seraj, R., and Islam, S.M.S. 2020. The k-means Algorithm: A Comprehensive Survey and Performance Evaluation. *Electronics*, 9(8): 1295.
- [2] Amel-Zadeh, A., and Serafeim, G. 2018. Why and How Investors Use ESG Information: Evidence from a Global Survey. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 74(3): 87-103. <https://doi.org/10.2469/faj.v74.n3.2>.
- [3] Audrino, F., Sigrist, F., & Ballinari, D. 2020. The Impact of Sentiment and Attention Measures on Stock Market Volatility. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 36(2), 334-357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2019.05.010>.
- [4] Bermejo Climent, R., Figuerola-Ferretti Garrigues, I., Paraskevopoulos, I., and Santos, A. 2021. ESG Disclosure and Portfolio Performance. *Risks*, 9(10): 172. <https://doi.org/10.3390/risks9100172>.
- [5] Cappucci, M. 2018. The ESG Integration Paradox. *Journal of Applied Corporate Finance*, 30(2): 22-28. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jacf.12296>.
- [6] Chen, S., Song, Y., and Gao, P. 2023. Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Performance and Financial Outcomes: Analyzing the Impact of ESG on Financial Performance. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 345: 118829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.118829>.
- [7] Chakraborty, D., Başağaoğlu, H., and Winterle, J. 2020. Interpretable vs. Noninterpretable Machine Learning Models for Data-driven Hydro-climatological Process Modeling. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 170: 114498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.114498>.
- [8] Cortzen, J.V., and Felfel, Y. 2023. Is ESG a Pathway to Alpha? Examining the Risk and Return of Sustainable Investing. Master's Thesis, Accounting, Strategy & Control, Contract no. 30180, Supervisor: Peter Belling, 107 pages.
- [9] D'Amato, V., D'Ecclesia, R.L., and Levantesi, S. 2021. Fundamental Ratios as Predictors of ESG Scores: A Machine Learning Approach. *Rivista di Matematica per le Scienze Economiche e Sociali*, 44(7): 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10203-021-00364-5>.
- [10] Del Vitto, A., Marazzina, D., and Stocco, D. 2023. ESG Ratings Explainability Through Machine Learning Techniques. *Annals of Operations Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-023-05288-9>.
- [11] Domínguez-Almendros, S., Benítez-Parejo, N., and Gonzalez-Ramirez, A.R. 2011. Logistic Regression Models. *Allergologia et Immunopathologia*, 39(5): 295-305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aller.2011.05.002>.
- [12] Dudek, G., Fiszeder, P., Kobus, P., and Orzeszko, W. 2024. Forecasting Cryptocurrencies Volatility Using Statistical and Machine Learning Methods: A Comparative Study. *Applied Soft Computing*, 151: 111132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2023.111132>.
- [13] Jurafsky, D., and Martin, J.H. 2024. Logistic Regression. In *Speech and Language Processing* (3rd ed.), pp. 77-91. Draft of August 20, 2024.
- [14] Khan, A.A., Chaudhari, O., and Chandra, R. 2024. A Review of Ensemble Learning and Data Augmentation Models for Class Imbalanced Problems: Combination, Implementation and Evaluation. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 244: 122778. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.122778>.
- [15] Kim, S., and Li, Z. 2021. Understanding the Impact of ESG Practices in Corporate Finance. *Sustainability*, 13(7): 3746. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13073746>.
- [16] Karrar, A.E. 2022. The Effect of Using Data Pre-Processing by Imputations in Handling Missing Values. *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Informatics (IJEI)*, 10(2): 375-384. <https://doi.org/10.52549/ijeie.v10i2.3730>.
- [17] Li, H., Guo, H., Hao, X., and Zhang, X. 2023. The ESG Rating, Spillover of ESG Ratings, and Stock Return: Evidence from Chinese Listed Firms. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 80: 102091. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacfin.2023.102091>.
- [18] Liu, Y., Osterrieder, J., Misheva, B.H., Koenigstein, N., and Baals, L. 2023. Navigating the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Landscape: Constructing a Robust and Reliable Scoring Engine. *Open Research Europe*, 3: 119. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16278.1>.
- [19] Mandas, M., Lahmar, O., Piras, L., and De Lisa, R. 2023. ESG in the Financial Industry: What Matters for Rating Analysts? *Research in International Business and Finance*, 66: 102045. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2023.102045>.

- [20] Masood, F. 2024. Assessing the Impact of Machine Learning Algorithms on Portfolio Optimization and Risk Management in the Era of Sustainable Investing. *International Journal of Emerging Multidisciplinaries Computer Science & Artificial Intelligence*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.54938/ijemdc sai.2024.03.1.294>.
- [21] Markowitz, H. 1952. Portfolio Selection. *The Journal of Finance*, 7(1): 77-91. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2975974>.
- [22] Pedersen, M. 2014. Portfolio Optimization and Monte Carlo Simulation. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2438121>.
- [23] Quaye, E., Tunaru, D., and Tunaru, R. 2024. Green-adjusted Share Prices: A Comparison Between Standard Investors and Investors with Green Preferences. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 74: 101314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfs.2024.101314>.
- [24] Rusu, S., Boloş, M.I., and Leordeanu, M. 2023. K-Means and Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering Analysis of ESG Scores, Yearly Variations, and Stock Returns: Insights from the Energy Sector in Europe and the United States. *Journal of Financial Studies*, 8(Special), 166-180. <https://doi.org/10.55654/JFS.2023.SP.11>.
- [25] Sariyer, G., and Taşkın, D. 2022. Clustering of Firms Based on Environmental, Social, and Governance Ratings: Evidence from BIST Sustainability Index. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 22(Supplement 2), S180-S188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2022.10.009>.
- [26] Sharpe, W.F. 1964. Capital Asset Prices: A Theory of Market Equilibrium under Conditions of Risk. *The Journal of Finance*, 19(3): 425-442. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2977928>.
- [27] Sharpe, W.F. 1966. Mutual Fund Performance. *The Journal of Business*, 39(1): 119-138. <https://doi.org/10.1086/294846>.
- [28] Sherwood, M.W., and Pollard, J. 2018. *Responsible Investing: An Introduction to Environmental, Social, and Governance Investments*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203712078>.
- [29] Shiplu, A.I., Rahman, M.M., and Watanobe, Y. 2024. A Robust Ensemble Machine Learning Model with Advanced Voting Techniques for Comment Classification. *Big Data Analytics in Astronomy, Science, and Engineering (BDA 2023)*. DOI:10.1007/978-3-031-58502-9_10.
- [30] Shrivastav, L., and Kumar, R. 2022. An Ensemble of Random Forest, Gradient Boosting Machine, and Deep Learning Methods for Stock Price Prediction. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 15(1): 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.4018/JITR.2022010102>.
- [31] Utz, S., Wimmer, M., and Steuer, R. 2015. Tri-Criterion Modeling for Constructing More-Sustainable Mutual Funds. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 246(1): 224-231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2015.04.035>.
- [32] Van Houdt, G., Mosquera, C., and Nápoles, G. 2020. A Review on the Long Short-Term Memory Model. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 53(1). DOI:10.1007/s10462-020-09838-1.
- [33] Viehs, M., Clark, G.L., and Feiner, A. 2014. From The Stockholder to The Stakeholder - How Sustainability Can Drive Financial Outperformance. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2508281>.
- [34] Wong, T.-T., and Yeh, P.-Y. 2019. Reliable Accuracy Estimates from k-Fold Cross Validation. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, PP(99): 1-1. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2019.2912815>.
- [35] Zeng, X., Zheng, L., and Cui, C. 2024. Leveraging AI and Machine Learning for ESG Data Analysis and Sustainable Investment Decision-making. *Applied and Computational Engineering*, 87(1): 209-214. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2755-2721/87/20241590>.